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CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES AS DETERMINANT OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BUSINESS EDUCATION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN ADAMAWA STATE

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Abstract

The research study examined classroom management techniques as determinants of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study stated two specific purposes, from which two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study consisted of 236 business education students and 38 business education lecturers from tertiary institutions in Adamawa. There was no sampling as the total population was used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 31-item structured questionnaire validated by three experts. A pilot test was conducted at Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri, Borno State on 20 business education lecturers and 20 students offering business education. Using Cronbach alpha method, a reliability coefficient of 0.96 was obtained. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using linear regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The results of the study revealed that lecturer-student relationship determined students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa. It was concluded that the poor interaction and interpersonal relationship that existed between the lecturers' and students' contributed to poor students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. Among the recommendations made was that the government should ensure that policy makers in the education sector devise more ways in the school system that will facilitate internal school arrangements for instructors to get involved in useful interactions and mentoring of students besides just giving academic instructions.

Keywords: Classroom management techniques, lecturer-student relationship, discipline, business education, academic performance.

Introduction

One of the major issues that have attracted wide spread attention in educational research is the teaching and learning processes. Of particular interest is students' academic learning issues and how it affects academic performance. No system of education can rise above the quality of its teachers (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). In the teaching learning environment, the teacher is the third party. The teacher mediates between the learners' characteristics and the forces of the environment. The thrust of the mediation is to ensure that permanent change in behaviour takes place. As an authority figure in the academic arena, the teacher does not only teach but he guides, transmits, interprets, counsels and is the last link in the chain of implementation of educational policy. Education is a

very important human activity as it helps societies in fashioning and modelling individuals so that they can be productive and function well in their environment. Mazer (2013), saw undergraduate degree is an academic program that follows graduation from high school, sometimes called first degrees, undergraduate degrees build upon secondary education and develop greater depth of professional knowledge. Undergraduate programs are conferred by higher learning institutions, such as colleges and universities.

According to Boit *et al.* (2012), the purpose of education is to equip the citizenry to reshape the society and eliminate inequality. The teacher is one of the most prominent factors in any educational system. The roles, duties, and responsibilities of the teachers are very substantial in realizing the goals of national education. In Nigeria, education is seen as an instrument for national development, and the interaction of persons and ideas are all aspects of education. It fosters the development of the individual, for each individual's sake, and for the general development of the society. It promotes the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around and also the acquisition of appropriate skills and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society (FRN, 2013). To carry out these functions, tertiary institutions require competent lecturers. A lecturer plays a significant role in a student's educational life and students' performance in their studies is really dependent on the way they learn. One of these factors may be how lecturers manage their classrooms in the teaching and learning process.

Classroom management in this study refers to the ability of a lecturer to create a good learning environment. Classroom management refers to the sum total of plan of actions taken by the lecturer in the classroom to bring about a conducive classroom environment that supports teaching and learning leading to success and achievement. Agbabi *et al.* (2013) saw classroom management as the process and strategies an educator uses to maintain a classroom environment that is conducive to students learning and success. Effective classroom management helps the lecturer to conduct smooth teaching and learning activities. The classroom is a unique unit where the teacher and the students interact for teaching and learning to take place. Grapragasem *et al.* (2015), saw classroom management as the actions lecturers take to create an environment that supports and facilitates both academic and social-emotional learning. Therefore, the lecturer has to create an environment conducive for effective teaching and learning in the classroom, to promote academic and social-emotional learning.

A classroom is a workplace where teaching and learning activities take place between lecturers and students. According to Grapragasem *et al.* (2015), lecturers have to plan their lessons, decide the learning objectives and conduct lessons in the classroom based on the students' needs and abilities. In order to achieve the learning objectives, lecturers have to create conducive classroom environment, interact with the students, monitor their progress and evaluate their achievements. Teachers face the up-hill task to educate students from various races, cultures and religions. Besides that, different languages and socioeconomic status are also challenges that require lecturers to be more productive and creative, while conducting teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Doyle (2011) identified two major tasks that lecturers have to shoulder while managing the classroom. The tasks are to facilitate learning among students, and also to establish order within the classroom so that learning can take place. These tasks are interdependent but they enhance teaching and learning process by promoting orderliness, an environment conducive to engaging students to actively participate in learning activities in the classroom. Classroom management techniques indices include lecturer-student relationship and discipline. These techniques are employed

by lecturers to ensure smooth teaching and learning. Lecturer-student relationship is recognized to be a formalized interpersonal association between an authority figure and a subordinate who interacts on nearly daily basis (Camp, 2011). A good individual relationship between lecturers and students is the foundation of successful programme of education.

According to Borba in Camp (2011), the importance of interpersonal relationships in people's lives cannot be overstated. People need to feel a sense of connectedness to another human being particularly to those we considered to be important and significant. Borba held that if students are to learn, they must feel comfortable in their instructional environment. The nature of the classroom environment has a powerful influence on how well students achieve educational outcomes (Asiyai, 2014). When lecturers have positive relationships with their students, they improve the classroom and environment, which results in more motivation (Varga, 2017). Research suggests that good teacher-student relationships are important for maintaining adolescents' interests and academic engagement in learning (Maulana *et al.* 2013). Varga (2017), observed that students who have positive relationships with their lecturers have better achievement outcomes on their tests and examinations. According to Varga the inverse is also true, negative lecturer -student relationships which correspond to worse student outcomes.

Galabawa in Mussa (2015) saw discipline as an act of subjecting someone to a code of behaviour that there is a widespread agreement that an orderly atmosphere is necessary in school for effective teaching and learning to take place. Discipline, according to Mussa (2015), is reasonable in the eyes of those who receive it and in the eyes of society as a whole. It is expected that the rules are known by all and are consistently enforced. In order for an action to be good, discipline must also be reasonable. The way lecturers manage their classrooms discipline is generally regarded as crucial factors in students' learning experiences (Nie *et al.* 2013). According to Mtsweni (2013), lecturers often try to keep their classrooms free from disruption. To do so, they need to manage the class and correct learners' behaviour in such a passionate way that encourages, motivates, and retains positive behaviour.

Taking into account that classroom management, classroom work and classroom discipline are inextricably linked, lecturers must develop accurate sense of what is best for the class in every moment (Lopes & Oliveira, 2017). Research suggests that students learning must not be sacrificed by the need for classroom order or classroom management. Conversely, lecturers must be aware that without a certain level of classroom order, student learning will suffer (Martinez *et al.* 2016). Perhaps the most striking evidence in the relation between academic achievement and classroom indiscipline is that majority of defiant classroom behavior is carried out by low-achieving students (Way, 2011). Lopes and Oliveira (2017), affirmed that high-achieving students only occasionally misbehave, that their eventual misbehavior tends to occur during classroom transitions, not during the lesson because they do not intend to interrupt the lesson, which low underachievers often do and this pattern has even been found in college and university students. As a consequence, academic underachievers increasingly miss out on learning opportunities, potentially worsening their behavioral and academic performance (Way, 2011).

Lopes and Oliveira (2017), observed that research has also shown that the gap between school underachievers and their peers tends to systematically deepen throughout schooling. The growing disaffection of underachievers significantly increases the likelihood of classroom misbehaviours and disruption. This process reduces the opportunity to learn and increases the likelihood of classroom misbehaviour, disciplinary referrals, learned helplessness, among others, in a seemingly endless cycle. Lopes and Oliveira labeled this process involving

the relation of the underachieving students with the peers to affect student academic performance in the long run. Mumo in Karanja and Bowen (2012), in her research study on student and indiscipline reported that discipline is considered vital for students' academic and social success. The author further stressed that a good academic qualification without a good foundation of discipline of the individuals is of no use to the individuals, their families and the society. Marzona in Grapragasem *et al.* (2015), observed that a classroom that is well managed will provide an environment in which teaching and learning can flourish. Therefore, business education lecturers need to acquire classroom management techniques that will motivate their students towards learning, and fostering desirable behaviour.

Aliyu (2013) stated that business education stresses the need for specialized instruction to prepare students for career in business, fundamental instruction to help students assume economic roles as consumers, workers and citizens and background instruction to assist students in preparing for professional careers requiring advanced study. Business educators must adopt effective teaching strategies that supports and facilitates positive students' academic performance.

Annie, Howard and Mildred in Aransi (2018) defined academic performance as the outcome of education that can be used to determine the extent to which a student, teacher and institution have achieved their educational goals. Aransi (2018), saw academic performance as the learning outcomes of students which include the knowledge, skills and ideas, acquired and obtained through their course of study within and outside the classroom situation. The extent to which students attain the set objectives depends largely on the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching carried out by the lecturer (Eze, 2014). AL-Mutairi (2011), Kang'ahi *et al.* (2012) affirmed that there are several factors that influence students' academic performances, but lecturers' competence remains one of the major determinants of students' academic achievements. According to Ganyaupfu (2013), teaching is a collaborative process, which encompasses interaction between the learners and the lecturer.

Lecturers' competence in the teaching process is a multidimensional concept that measures numerous interrelated aspects of sharing knowledge with learners, which include classroom management techniques, teaching methods and commitment of motivated teachers. Therefore, consistent evaluation of the aforementioned factors is imperative, since the competence of a lecturer is directly measured by students' academic achievements (Muzenda, 2013).

According to AL-Mutairi (2011), students' academic performances are influenced by numerous factors applicable from one context to another. The broad dimensions of such factors include socioeconomic status, academic and institutional arrangements, students learning approaches as well as individual student's attributes. History has proven that lecturers have an important influence on students' academic performance. They play crucial role in educational attainments because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action during interaction with the students, engaged in the learning activity and process (Akiri, 2013). Organized classrooms increase engagement and reduce distractions leading to quality teaching and learning. A lecturer needs a variety of methods to identify strengths and weaknesses of individual learners, plan differentiated instructional activities for diverse learners and assess students' knowledge for the purpose of integrating multiple pathways of instruction namely lesson planning, instructional strategies, identifying students learning approaches and classroom management techniques. It is on the basis of this background therefore, that the study examined learning approaches

and classroom management techniques as determinants of students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Statement of Problem

The consequences of not addressing the problem of students' academic performance are numerous and dire. Students by their nature get involved in many activities outside their studies. When students lose interest in their studies, failure rate becomes higher. Students' academic performance is important in education. Despite the huge resources provided by government; results in the required quantum and quality are not commensurate. The researcher observed from personal experiences and group discussions with other business educators in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State that students usually fail in examinations owing to poor classroom management techniques.

Classroom management techniques engaged by lecturers may be related to students' academic performance. Acharu and Solomon (2014), support the above assertion and stated that one of the major problems inhibiting better academic performance is poor classroom management, which has affected students' achievement and academic performance. Teachers are identified as critical factors when it comes to imparting knowledge to students and development of a nation's work force. The classroom management techniques employed by teachers may have contributed to poor students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Emaikwu (2019) revealed that WAEC results of May/June 2011-2017 in business studies subjects which showed the percentage of failures nationwide as 68.24% (2011), 74.15% (2012), and 80% (2013), 83.09% (2014), 88.01% (2015), 90.20% (2016) and 93% (2017) respectively. The mass failure in business studies subjects may be attributed to many factors which seem hidden. This calls for investigation. Could it be approaches used by teachers? Could it be incompetence on the part of teachers? Could it be laziness on the part of students? Could poor students' academic performance be associated with fall in general standard of education? Could present students' poor academic performance have any relationship with their previous school foundations? These are the questions that require relevant answers.

The poor students' academic performance evidenced in the final year students' results in Business Education Department at Modibbo Adama University, Yola and Federal College of Education, Yola is of utmost concern. The results over a period of time revealed a decline in students Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) with higher number of students on probation in the aforementioned tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. As reflected in the 2017 convocation proceedings of MAU, Yola, in 2011/2012 academic session, 129 students were earlier admitted to study B. Sc. (Ed.) in Business Education, and by 2016/2017 academic session, only 51 students out of the 129 successfully graduated (MAU, 2017). This situation makes the students, lecturers, parents, government, school management and members of senate of MAU, Yola to trade blame for the poor academic performance. Students complained about lecturers' classroom management techniques as the major causes of the poor academic performances.

As a result of these differences on the opinion and complaints made by lecturers, students, parents, university guidance and counsellors, school administrators especially during the last convocation held at MAU, Yola in 2017 on the decline in students' academic performance and ratio of students enrolment to their graduation,

persuaded the researcher to examine whether the classroom management techniques used by lecturers in Business Education programmes especially in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State may have contributed to the present poor students' academic performance considering it is one of the educational disadvantage state in Nigeria. This prompted the researcher to carry out the present study, with the aim of determining the veracity of the claims and proffering possible solutions, using empirical evidences.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the extent classroom management techniques are determinants of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. Specifically, the study determined the extent:

1. Lecturer-student relationship serves as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.
2. Lecturers' discipline serves as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Research Questions

Based on the specific purposes, the following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does lecturer-student relationship serve as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State?
2. To what extent does lecturers' discipline serve as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: Lecturer-student relationship does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.
- H₀₂: Lecturers' discipline does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research method. Descriptive survey design is a design that deals with collecting, organizing and analysing data. Kabir (2016) stated descriptive survey is used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena and to describe what exists with respect to variables or conditions in a situation. The population of the study comprised 236 business education students and 38 lecturers in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. This study used NCE III students of the Colleges of Education and 500 Level students of the University respectively. Their CGPA for 2016/2017 and 2017/2018 academic sessions were used. There are three institutions offering business education programme in Adamawa State. These are: Modibbo Adama University, Yola, College of Education, Yola, and College of Education, Hong. The whole population was used as a sample since the population was not large. Two instruments were used for data collection: a structured questionnaire and students' academic performance proforma. The questionnaire measured classroom management techniques and

it was tagged 'Classroom Management Techniques' (CMT). The second instrument used in the study was the proforma to collect the academic performance of students. This was used to obtain students' cumulative grade point average (CGPA) in business education. The Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) of the students was categorized as follows; A- 70-100 scores = 5.00, B- 60-69 scores = 4.00, C- 50-59 scores = 3.00, D- 45-49 scores = 2.00, E- 40-44 scores = 1.00. The instrument was validated by two experts from business education who are not below the rank of Senior Lecturer. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha method. Thus, the result gave reliability co-efficient of 0.96. Mean and standard deviation were used to examine the data gathered to address the study questions, and regression statistic was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was set at 2.50, and for the hypotheses, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance if the observed probability value of the null hypothesis was less than or equal to the fixed value (0.05).

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does lecturer-student relationship serve as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the extent lecturer-student relationship serve as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State

S/N	Item Statements	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1.	A lecturers' friendliness stimulates interest in the learning of the students.	3.14	0.68	Moderate Extent
2.	Good lecturer-student relationship enables easy control of inappropriate behaviours in students.	3.06	1.00	Moderate Extent
3.	Good lecturer-student relationship is essential for effective learning process.	3.25	0.65	Moderate Extent
4.	A better relationship between lecturers and students positively affects the quality of students' motivation to learn.	3.02	1.00	Moderate Extent
5.	Good lecturer-student relationship brings about interesting classroom-learning experiences.	3.04	0.79	Moderate Extent
6.	A good Lecturer-student relationship holds high expectations for learners.	3.19	0.60	Moderate Extent
7.	A teacher-student interaction within the class engenders solid understanding of the nature of effective teaching and learning process.	3.21	0.79	Moderate Extent
8.	Good lecturer-student relationship makes students feel comfortable in front of the class, which is essential to student's success or failure.	3.26	0.59	Moderate Extent
9.	Lecturer-student relationship promotes students' engagement in the learning process.	3.01	0.68	Moderate Extent
10.	A good lecturer-student relationship facilitates a welcoming environment, which make students to perform effectively tasks they find personally important.	3.01	1.04	Moderate Extent
11.	Lecturer-student relationship creates positive learning environment that enhances the joy of learning.	3.03	0.65	Moderate Extent
Weighted Average		3.11	0.77	Moderate Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Analysis of Data in Table 1 reveals that the respondents generally indicated that all the constructs on what extent does lecturer-student relationship serve as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State to a moderate extent.

Table 1 shows a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.11 and 0.77 (Mean = 3.11, SD = 0.77) which means that the respondents uniformly indicated moderate extent for all the constructs. This implies lecturer-student relationship serve as a determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education to a moderate extent in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Research Question 2: To what extent does lecturers’ discipline serve as a determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the extent lecturer’ discipline serve as a determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State

S/N	Item Statements	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
12.	Good class control creates a good learning environment.	3.23	0.46	Moderate Extent
13.	Lecturers discipline styles encourage students to put on positive attitude in the lesson.	3.07	0.78	Moderate Extent
14.	Discipline creates an environment that facilitates effective teaching and learning.	3.11	0.98	Moderate Extent
15.	Discipline helps lecturers to conduct smooth teaching and learning activities.	3.02	0.85	Moderate Extent
16.	Good class control helps lecturers to monitor the academic progress of the students.	3.00	0.75	Moderate Extent
17.	Good class control helps the lecturers to evaluate student’s achievement in various subjects.	3.16	0.92	Moderate Extent
18.	The establishment of order within the classroom by the lecturer facilitates teaching and learning process.	3.24	0.58	Moderate Extent
19.	Orderliness within a classroom brings about an environment that supports easy instructions.	3.12	0.76	Moderate Extent
20.	Orderliness within the classroom helps in regulating the sequence of events towards achieving educational goals.	3.06	0.71	Moderate Extent
21.	Organized classroom increase engagement leading to quality teaching and learning.	3.23	0.56	Moderate Extent
22.	Organized classroom reduces distractions leading to quality teaching and learning.	3.07	0.99	Moderate Extent
23.	Orderliness within classroom prevents disruptive behavior of students in the class.	3.12	0.99	Moderate Extent
24.	Orderliness within classroom make students achieves the learning goals.	3.02	0.75	Moderate Extent
25.	Discipline corrects learner’s misbehaviours.	3.00	0.75	Moderate Extent
26.	Classroom orderliness promotes easy flow of instruction	3.08	1.01	Moderate Extent
27.	Classroom orderliness involves active participation of the students in teaching and learning process.	3.24	0.58	Moderate Extent
28.	Punishment in school brings about the desired change in behaviour.	3.04	0.76	Moderate Extent
29.	Punishment in the school system teaches students accountability for their mistakes.	3.06	0.71	Moderate Extent
30.	Punishment teaches students the relationship between their behaviors and their learning outcomes.	3.23	0.46	Moderate Extent
31.	A democratic form of discipline leads to a healthy classroom environment that in turn promotes desire for knowledge.	3.07	0.78	Moderate Extent
Weighted Average		3.11	0.76	Moderate extent

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Analysis of Data in Table 2 reveals that the respondents generally indicated that all the constructs on lecturers’ discipline are rated to moderate extent.

Table 2 shows a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.11 and 0.76 (Mean = 3.11, SD = 0.76) which means that the respondents uniformly indicated moderate extent for all the constructs. This implies that lecturers’ discipline serves as a determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education to a moderate extent in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Test of Hypotheses

The two null hypotheses were tested using linear regression at 0.05 level of significance. The summary of the test of hypotheses are presented in Tables 3 to 6 as follows:

H₀₁ Lecturer-student relationship does not significantly determine undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Table 3: Summary of Regression Analysis of lecturer-student relationship as determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	229	0.921	0.849	0.848

- a. Predictor (constant): Lecturer-student relationship.
- b. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance.

Table 4: Test of Significance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T		Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	0.546	.113		4.828	0.000	0.322	0.769
Lecturer-student Relationship	0.856	0.032	0.921	26.84	0.000	0.793	0.919

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance.
 Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Table 3 summarizes the results of regression analysis on lecturer-student relationship as determinant of undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education. The result indicates that there is a positive correlation between lecturer-student relationship and undergraduate students’ academic performance (R = 0.92) while R-squared is 0.849 which means that the independent variable (lecturer-student relationship) explained 84.9% variations of the dependent variable (academic performance).

The test of significance results as presented in Table 4 shows that lecturer-student relationship statistically significantly determines undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State (B = 0.857; $t_{(228)} = 26.480$, P = 0.000). It indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, there is enough evidence that lecturer-student relationship significantly determines undergraduate students’ academic performance in business education. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that lecturer-

student relationship significantly determines undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

H₀₂: Lecturers' discipline does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State

Table 5: Summary of Regression Analysis of lecturers' discipline as determinant of students' academic performance in Business Education

Model	N	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	229	0.093	0.009	0.004

- a. Predictor (constant): Lecturers' Discipline
- b. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance.

Table 6: Test of Significance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	65.541	8.697		7.536	0.000	48.403	82.679
	Lecturers' Discipline Techniques	3.581	2.551	0.093	1.404	0.162	8.609	1.446

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance.
 Source: Field Survey, 2022.

Table 5 summarizes the results of regression analysis on lecturers' discipline as determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education. The result indicates that there is a positive relationship between lecturers' discipline and students' academic performance ($R = 0.093$) while R-squared is 0.009 which means that the independent variable (lecturers' discipline) explained 0.09% variations of the dependent variable (academic performance).

The test of significance results as presented in Table 6 shows that lecturers' discipline does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State ($B = 3.581$; $t_{(228)} = 1.404$, $P = 0.162$). It indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, there is enough evidence that lecturers' discipline does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education. Based on this, the null hypothesis is not rejected and it is concluded that lecturers' discipline does not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

Discussion of Findings

Analysis of the first research question which sought to know the extent lecturer-student relationship determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria, showed a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.11 and 0.77 (Mean = 3.11, SD = 0.77) which meant that the respondents uniformly indicated moderate extent for all the constructs. This implied

that lecturer-student relationship served as a determinant of undergraduate students' academic performance in business education to a moderate extent in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

To further support this result, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) in Table 4 showed that lecturer-student relationship significantly determined undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State ($B = 0.857$; $t_{(228)} = 26.480$, $P = 0.000$). It indicated that at 0.05 level of significance, there was enough evidence that lecturer-student relationship significantly determined academic performance of undergraduate business education students. Based on the findings of this study, the null hypothesis was rejected.

The study found that based on the analysis of the data collected from the respondents that if students are to learn, they must feel comfortable in their relationship with their lecturers. This finding is in line with Allen *et al.* (2013) who stated that good lecturer-student relationship makes students feel comfortable in front of class which is essential to students' academic success or failure. The result of this study also agreed with Varga (2017) who held that when lecturers have positive relationships with their students, they improve the classroom environment which results in more motivation and better academic performance. The findings of this study is in agreement with Camp (2011) who observed that there is abundant research stressing the importance of lecturers caring for their students and believing that these students can learn and holding high expectations for them as learners. The findings of this study is also in agreement with Maulana *et al.* (2013) who observed that good lecturer-student relationship is important for maintaining students interest and academic engagement in the learning process. Likewise a positive lecturer-student relationship is essential for motivating and engaging students towards increased positive productivity and academic achievement.

When lecturers care for, respect and show personal involvement in such a way that students are aware of it, the students are more highly motivated to work hard and which will lead to better academic performance. Thus, in view of the supporting literatures, the result of the study revealed that lecturer-student relationship tremendously determined undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Analysis of the second research question which sought to know the extent lecturers' discipline determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria, showed a calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation of 3.11 and 0.76 (Mean = 3.11, SD = 0.76) which meant that the respondents uniformly indicated moderate extent for all the constructs. This implied that lecturers' discipline determined undergraduate students' in business education to a moderate extent in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State.

The test of the null hypothesis (H_{02}) in Table 6 showed that lecturers' discipline did not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State ($B = 3.581$; $t_{(228)} = 1.404$, $P = 0.162$). It indicates that at 0.05 level of significance, there was enough evidence that lecturers' discipline did not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education. Based on the result of this finding, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

The findings of this study are in line with the findings of Galabawa in Mussa (2015) who viewed discipline as an activity of subjecting someone to a code of behaviour that there is a widespread agreement that an orderly atmosphere is necessary in the school and classroom for effective teaching and learning to take place. Omari in

Sunday-Piaroi (2018) affirmed that punishment does not teach the correct behaviour, that it destroys even the opportunity to demonstrate the acceptable behaviour. Viewing from the angle of Cotton in Närhi *et al.* (2015), punishment in the classroom are expected to teach students accountability for their mistakes, (that is, to teach them the relationship between their behaviours and the outcome). This result is in contradiction with the study conducted by George *et al.* (2017) who opined that classroom management technique is aimed at producing conducive learning environment where students can learn with ease and perform better academically. Marzano in Grapragasem *et al.* (2015) also held a contrary view when he stated that a well-managed classroom provides an environment in which teaching and learning can flourish that will result to academic success. In support of this view, Njoroge and Nyabuto (2014) viewed discipline as a democratic form of discipline which leads to healthy classroom environment that in turn promotes respect for education and a desire for knowledge. Karanja and Bowen (2012) affirmed that the upshot is that student disturbances negatively affect academic performance. The result of this study revealed that lecturers' discipline did not determine students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

After the statistical analysis of the data, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions that lecturers' discipline did not significantly determine undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. Lecturer-student relationship significantly determined undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The implication of the aforementioned revealed that the poor interaction and interpersonal relationship that existed between the lecturers and students contributed to poor undergraduate students' academic performance in business education in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State. Based on that, it was concluded that if lecturers instil good interaction with positive lecturer-student relationship it would motivate student's class achievements which would result to better academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained and conclusion drawn, the researcher made the following recommendations:

1. Government should ensure that policy makers in the education sector devise more ways in the school system that will facilitate internal school arrangements for instructors to get involved in useful interactions and mentoring of students besides just giving academic instructions.
2. Lecturers' should not insist so much on students' discipline as it does not significantly influence students' academic performance.

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